

The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (2.2) and Agent-Based modelling for Archaeologists

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Abstract: This document describes the various competences that are addressed in the tutorials for Agent-Based modelling for Archaeologists. This is described using the competence area's, competences and the proficiency levels from the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (2.2). This document describes the starting levels and the levels gained when learning from the tutorials.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction	2
2 Starting point: competence level	3
3 English level	4
4 Proficiency levels and the ABM tutorials	4
4.1 Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM	4
4.2 Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM	5
4.3 Tutorial 3: Expanded ABM skills	6
4.4 Tutorial 4: Intermediate ABM	6
4.5 Tutorial 5: How to Model	7
4.6 Tutorials 1-5: proficiency development	8
5 Competence development in the tutorials	8
5.1 Competence Area 1. Information and data literacy	9
5.2 Competence Area 2. Communication and collaboration	9
5.3 Competence Area 3. Digital content creation	9
5.4 Competence Area 5. Problem solving	10
6 Proficiency levels after the tutorials	10
References	10

1 Introduction

The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (version 2.2), or DigComp, provides a framework for digital skills and knowledge. It forms solid and technology-neutral basis to understand of digital skills and can be used for framing policy (European Commission, Joint Research Centre et al. 2022).

The DigComp outlines 5 competence areas (Figure 1):

- Information and data literacy
- Communication and collaboration
- Digital content creation
- Safety
- Problem solving

The competence area's are broadly defined and encompass all aspects of working with digital means and tools. Area 1. *Information and data literacy* describes the abilities to find, evaluate and store digital data and information. Area 2. *Communication and collaboration* is to evaluate the competencies related using digital means to interact, communicate and collaborate using digital means. This can be used to describe the abilities of one to participate in the digital society and being able to present yourself digitally. The third area, *Digital content creation*, is about the ability to create and edit digital content, including copyright and licenses. The area 4. *Safety* is used to describe how well a person can protect devices, data and privacy in a digital environment. The protection is not only digital, but also related physical protection. In addition, the environmental impact of technologies is also described in this area. The fifth and last competence area is *Problem solving*, which is used to describe the ability to identify needs and problems and to resolve these issues. Problem solving includes innovation and staying up-to-date with developments in the field.

Figure 1: Dimension 1 of the 5 DigComp area's (source: European Commission, Joint Research Centre et al. 2022: 7 (Figure 3)).

These competence area's consist of 5 numbered dimensions:

1. Competence area;
2. Competence;
3. Proficiency level;
4. Examples of knowledge, skills and attitudes;
5. Use cases.

Each competence can be described using the proficiency levels. There are also generally described (Figure 2).

T.6 Main keywords that feature the proficiency levels								
4 OVERALL LEVELS	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised	
8 GRANULAR LEVELS	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
COMPLEXITY OF TASKS	Simple task	Simple task	Well-defined and routine tasks, and straightforward problems	Tasks, and well-defined and non-routine problems	Different tasks and problems	Most appropriate tasks	Resolve complex problems with limited solutions	Resolve complex problems with many interacting factors
AUTONOMY	With guidance	Autonomy and with guidance when needed	On my own	Independent and according to my needs	Guiding others	Able to adapt to others in a complex context	Integrate to contribute to the professional practice and to guide others	Propose new ideas and processes to the field
COGNITIVE DOMAIN	Remembering	Remembering	Understanding	Understanding	Applying	Evaluating	Creating	Creating

Figure 2: Proficiency levels of competencies (source: European Commission, Joint Research Centre et al. 2022: 71 (T.6)).

Please note that: “The eight proficiency levels are inspired by the structure and vocabulary of the European Qualification Framework (EQF), however with no link to the qualifications or education and training systems.” (European Commission, Joint Research Centre et al. 2022: 70)

For the European Qualification Framework (EQF): see <https://europa.eu/europass/en/europass-tools/european-qualifications-framework>.

2 Starting point: competence level

The learning and teaching material for ABM for archaeologists assumes that the users have completed secondary education. It is suitable for archaeologists with at least some background in archaeology and preferably after at least the first year of a Bachelor study in Archaeology (preferably above EQF levels 4 or 5). In addition, for professionals working in archaeology and some experience with computers, the teaching material should also be easy to understand and to follow.

Following the DigComp 2.2 we have defined the minimal level that the users should have to be able to work with the material delivered (see Figure 3). That does not mean that people with lower proficiency levels are not able to work through the material, but it might be harder work to complete the assignments and lessons. The proficiency levels that will be gained through the tutorials will be explained in section

Dimension 1: Competence Area	Dimension 2: Competence	Dimension 3: Proficiency level (minimum level expected)
1. Information and data literacy	1.1 Browsing, Searching and Filtering Data, Information and Digital Content	6
	1.2 Evaluating Data, Information And Digital Content	6
	1.3 Managing Data, Information And Digital Content	5
2. Communication and collaboration	2.1 Interacting Through Digital Technologies	5
	2.2 Sharing Through Digital Technologies	4
	2.3 Engaging Citizenship Through Digital Technologies	4
	2.4 Collaborating Through Digital Technologies	3
	2.5 Netiquette	3
	2.6 Managing Digital Identity	3
3. Digital content creation	3.1 Developing Digital Content	4
	3.2 Integrating And Re-Elaborating Digital Content	5
	3.3 Copyright And Licences	3
	3.4 Programming	1
4. Safety	4.1 Protecting Devices	2
	4.2 Protecting Personal Data And Privacy	2
	4.3 Protecting Health And Well-Being	2
	4.4 Protecting The Environment	2
5. Problem solving	5.1 Solving Technical Problems	3
	5.2 Identifying Needs And Technological Responses	4
	5.3 Creatively Using Digital Technology	3
	5.4 Identifying Digital Competence Gaps	4

Figure 3: Competencies and the minimal levels of proficiency needed to learn ABM using our material.

3 English level

The tutorials are all in English and some proficiency is needed. We have used the “Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment (CEFR)” (Council of Europe 2020) to describe the minimal levels of English needed to be able to use the teaching material (see also <https://europa.eu/europass/en/common-european-framework-reference-language-skills>). We assume that learners have at least the Reading B1 level, but Reading B2 is recommended.

4 Proficiency levels and the ABM tutorials

We have created several tutorials for learning Agent-Based Modeling (ABM). While ABM can be considered a highly specialized competency in general, learning something new should always start with building a foundation and working towards more advanced levels (Figure 2). For our teaching material we have chosen to create tutorials that are self-guided. The student will start with the basics and will slowly become proficient to an advanced or even specialized level.

The following tutorials will be discussed:

- Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM
- Tutorial 2: Beginning with NetLogo
- Tutorial 3: Expanded ABM skills
- Tutorial 4: Intermediate ABM
- Tutorial 5: How to Model

4.1 Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM

In this tutorial the learner will learn what simulations and agent-based models are and how they can help in archaeological research. This tutorial consists of 4 lessons:

1. Introduction to Simulation
2. Introduction to ABM
3. How ABM can help
4. Introduction to NetLogo Interface

The first two lessons introduce the learner into simulation in general and Agent-Based Modelling in specific. Various concepts related to ABM are introduced and the first concepts within NetLogo are explained. The third lesson aims to explain how ABMs are used in archaeological research. The final lesson introduces the learner to the NetLogo Interface and the difference between the Interactive and Authoring mode. This tutorial builds a foundation for working in NetLogo and with ABM. All activity stays within the intermediate level, although higher levels might be touched upon. (Figure 4).

Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
1 Introduction to Simulation									
2 Introduction to ABM									
3 How ABM can help									
4 Introduction to NetLogo Interface									

Figure 4: Development of the proficiency levels for tutorial 1.

4.2 Tutorial 2: Beginning with NetLogo

In this tutorial the learner will learn the basics of NetLogo by making your first simulation on the Out of Africal dispersal of *Homo sapiens* (Young and Bettinger 1995). The learner will work with basic NetLogo syntax and learn how to set up a simulation and visualize their outcomes. This tutorial consists of 9 lessons:

1. The Setup Procedure
2. Changing the world
3. The Go Procedure
4. Creating Custom Procedures
5. Creating Variables
6. Custom Environment
7. Advanced Environment
8. Complex Behavior
9. Creating Plots

Tutorial 2: Beginning with NetLogo	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 The Setup Procedure								
2 Changing the world								
3 The Go Procedure								
4 Creating Custom Procedures								
5 Creating Variables								
6 Custom Environment								
7 Advanced Environment								
8 Complex Behavior								
9 Creating Plots								

Figure 5: Development of the proficiency levels for tutorial 2.

This tutorial intends to guide the learner from the intermediate to the advanced level of proficiency. The learning curve is relatively gentle. This is achieved by learning to work with the NetLogo web interface. The primitives are introduced and initialization phase of a simple ABM is gone through. The world within NetLogo's world (including dimensions, coordinates, origin) and how to alter it are explained and experience in a hands-on approach. The learners learn about simple simulation loops and how to use primitives. The advanced level is achieved with the custom procedures and variables. In addition, if-statements are introduced and more complex versions thereof. Exporting information using plots is also explained (Figure 5).

4.3 Tutorial 3: Expanded ABM skills

In this tutorial, the learner will build a simple trade model (Romanowska 2018), picking up more advanced NetLogo coding along the way, such as loops, lists and reporters. The learner will be introduced to some techniques like modular code development and debugging which will become important with this increased coding complexity. This tutorial consists of 7 lessons:

1. Introduction
2. Building the Model
3. Introduction to Breeds
4. Introduction to Loops
5. Introduction to Reporters
6. Introduction to Lists
7. Debugging

Tutorial 3: Expanded ABM skills	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 Introduction								
2 Building the Model								
3 Introduction to Breeds								
4 Introduction to Loops								
5 Introduction to Reporters								
6 Introduction to Lists								
7 Debugging								

Figure 6: Development of the proficiency levels for tutorial 3.

This tutorial intends to guide the learner from the intermediate to the advanced and highly specialised level of proficiency. This is achieved by improving development through using modular code, pseudocode and annotating the code. In addition, custom agent breeds are introduced. Visualization with labels and reporters, plots and monitors are learned. The use of loops is further explained. Debugging is learned in lesson 7. This can be very advanced, since it involves knowledge of the NetLogo-language combined with problem solving of unexpected behaviour.

4.4 Tutorial 4: Intermediate ABM

In this tutorial the learner will work with Sugarscape simulations (Epstein and Axtell 1996) to further expand your ABM and NetLogo skills. The learner will learn how to set up more complex interactions between agents and the environment. Furthermore, the basics of setting up good experiments and validating models will be explained. This tutorial consists of 8 lessons:

1. Introduction
2. Simple Sugarscape
3. Visualizing your model's behaviour
4. Patch Agency
5. Toy Landscape
6. Plots and Monitoring
7. Validation and Simulation as Scientific Experiment
8. Dynamic Lists

Tutorial 4: Intermediate ABM	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 Introduction								
2 Simple Sugarscape								
3 Visualizing your model's behavior								
4 Patch Agency								
5 Toy Landscape								
6 Plots and Monitoring								
7 Validation and Simulation as Scientific Experiment								
8 Dynamic Lists								

Figure 7: Development of the proficiency levels for tutorial 4.

This tutorial intends to guide the learner from the (intermediate and) advanced level to the highly specialised level of proficiency. In this tutorial more complex agent-environment interaction is further learned, including learning ways to visualize the environment and how to give more agency to patches. Creating toy landscapes are central to lesson 5. The learner also learns the basics of setting up experiments in NetLogo and how to use monitors and flexible plots to understand the results. The validation of agent-based models is an important concept of designing a good experiment. The finale step, is to compare simulation results with the archaeological record. The last lesson is aimed at learning syntax to make lists more dynamic and how to refactor code.

4.5 Tutorial 5: How to Model

In this tutorial the learner will learn more about how to actually incorporate agent-based modelling in research. This tutorial focusses less on programming in NetLogo and more on the model development process. The learner will learn about the different phases in modelling and how to export data from models. This tutorial consists of 5 lessons:

1. How to Model 101
2. The Conceptual Phase
3. The Technical Phase
4. The Dissemination Phase
5. Exporting Data

Tutorial 5: How to Model	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced	Highly specialised		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1 How to Model 101								
2 The Conceptual Phase								
3 The Technical Phase								
4 The Dissemination Phase								
5 Exporting Data								

Figure 8: Development of the proficiency levels for tutorial 5.

This tutorial touches upon various levels, but mainly between the intermediate and highly specialised level of proficiency. This tutorial is approaches more theoretical aspects in a practical environment. The learner leans about the model development process starting with the conceptual phase of the model development. Good and bad research questions for modelling are explained and the difference between them. The learner needs to understand how to pick the right modelling technique. The learner should understand the importance of properly conceptualizing a model before starting the technical phase of the model development. In this phase parametrisation, designing experiments and the analyses and interpretation of the models are important. Learning about the dissemination phase of the model development is aimed at understanding (the importance of) publishing models and replication. In addition, learning how to export results from NetLogo using basic export primitives is explained. The BehaviorSpace is explained to enable the learners to analyse the output of models.

4.6 Tutorials 1-5: proficiency development

The best way to learn ABM from scratch to an advanced level is to work through all tutorials (see Figure 9). The first starts on a foundational level, tutorial 2 guides the learners through the intermediate level and from tutorial 3 the advanced level will be central to the learning experience. Tutorials 4 and 5 aim at the specialised level, while still touching upon gaining advanced experience.

	Foundation		Intermediate		Advanced		Highly specialised	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM	■							
Tutorial 2: Beginning with NetLogo		■						
Tutorial 3: Expanded ABM skills			■					
Tutorial 4: Intermediate ABM				■				
Tutorial 5: How to Model					■			

Figure 9: The progress through the subsequent proficiency levels while learning ABM with the tutorials.

5 Competence development in the tutorials

The tutorials deal with various competence area's (Figure 10), but mainly focusses on 1. *Information and data literacy*, 3. *Digital content creation*, and 5. *Problem solving*. Competence area 2. *Communication and collaboration* is minimally addressed, because the tutorials are aimed at helping an individual to learn. While competence area 4. *Safety* is always important, it is not directly relevant for learning ABM and this is not addressed. We assume that users have some basic understanding of digital safety, but it is beyond the scope of this course to include teaching materials.

	1. Information and data literacy			2. Communication and collaboration					3. Digital content creation				4. Safety				5. Problem solving				
	1.1 Browsing, Searching and Filtering Data, Information And Digital Content	1.2 Evaluating Data, Information And Digital Content	1.3 Managing Data, Information And Digital Content	2.1 Interacting Through Digital Technologies	2.2 Sharing Through Digital Technologies	2.3 Engaging Citizenship Through Digital Technologies	2.4 Collaborating Through Digital Technologies	2.5 Netiquette	2.6 Managing Digital Identity	3.1 Developing Digital Content	3.2 Integrating And Re-Elaborating Digital Content	3.3 Copyright And Licenses	3.4 Programming	4.1 Protecting Devices	4.2 Protecting Personal Data And Privacy	4.3 Protecting Health And Well-Being	4.4 Protecting The Environment	5.1 Solving Technical Problems	5.2 Identifying Needs And Technological Responses	5.3 Creatively Using Digital Technology	5.4 Identifying Digital Competence Gaps
Tutorial 1: Introduction to ABM																					
1 Introduction to Simulation																					
2 Introduction to ABM																					
3 How ABM can help																					
4 Introduction to NetLogo Interface																					
Tutorial 2: Beginning with NetLogo																					
1 The Setup Procedure																					
2 Changing the world																					
3 The Go Procedure																					
4 Creating Custom Procedures																					
5 Creating Variables																					
6 Custom Environment																					
7 Advanced Environment																					
8 Complex Behavior																					
9 Creating Plots																					
Tutorial 3																					
1 Introduction																					
2 Building the Model																					
3 Introduction to Breeds																					
4 Introduction to Lumps																					
5 Introduction to Responses																					
6 Introduction to Leta																					
7 Debugging																					
Tutorial 4																					
1 Introduction																					
2 Simple Sugars																					
3 Visualizing your model's behavior																					
4 Agent Agency																					
5 Toy Landscape																					
6 Pica and Monitoring																					
7 Validation and Simulation as Scientific Experiment																					
8 Dynamic Leta																					
Tutorial 5																					
1 How to Model '01																					
2 The Concorde Phase																					
3 The Technical Phase																					
4 The Determination Phase																					
5 Exporting Data																					

Figure 10: Competence development for the two tutorials. Darker green indicates that this is central in the tutorial. Lighter green indicates that this competence is touched upon, but not in depth.

5.1 Competence Area 1. Information and data literacy

The tutorials mainly address 1.2 Evaluating Data, Information And Digital Content and 1.3 Managing Data, Information And Digital Content. The users learn about working with data, being critical of their digital content and how to model and manage the data in the context of an ABM. For tutorial 2 the user is expected to be able to lookup information using the NetLogo(Web) dictionary (<http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/bind/> or <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/docs/dictionary.html>).

5.2 Competence Area 2. Communication and collaboration

The tutorials mainly address 2.1 Interacting Through Digital Technologies, because the users are constantly interacting with digital technologies, but communications is not relevant for the tutorials. However, during the workshops given in the course of the project, participants interacted with each other and the teachers.

5.3 Competence Area 3. Digital content creation

This is one of the main competence areas for the ABM-teaching material. In the process of learning ABM the users are constantly 3.1 Developing Digital Content and 3.2 Integrating And Re-Elaborating Digital Content. The material does not touch upon 3.3 Copyright And Licences, but we assume that users have a general understanding. A very important aspect of learning ABM is 3.4 Programming. The users are exploring the possibilities and chances of programming an ABM. The users are expected to learn both syntax and more general concepts such as modular code development, loops, lists and commenting and documenting code.

5.4 Competence Area 5. Problem solving

The competence area is very important and is closely tied to 3.4 Programming, since programming involves a lot of problem solving. In addition, the creation of a highly complex ABM consists of problem solving all the time, including debugging. All competencies are addressed: 5.1 *Solving Technical Problems*, is common when writing code, learning about coding, error handling and going from pseudocode to real code. The competence 5.2 *Identifying Needs And Technological Responses*, is a central issue of the course, while 5.3 *Creatively Using Digital Technology* is an important aspect of learning to think in models and develop models themselves. In tutorial 2 various aspects of 5.4 *Identifying Digital Competence Gaps*, are relevant, since this tutorial will force the user to remember code and commands and forces the user to assess their knowledge and skills.

6 Proficiency levels after the tutorials

The developed tutorials aim to improve the digital competence of European learners. In Figure 3 the minimal levels of proficiency are explained. When a learner has worked through all tutorials this will have improved the level of proficiency on the various competencies. For dimension 3 this means that various levels have increased after learning from the tutorials, but for some competencies the proficiency has not increased because these level 2 competences are not part of the tutorials.

Dimension 1: Competence Area	Dimension 2: Competence	Dimension 3: Proficiency level (minimum level expected)	Dimension 3: ABM - Proficiency level after tutorials
1. Information and data literacy	1.1 Browsing, Searching and Filtering Data, Information and Digital Content	6	8
	1.2 Evaluating Data, Information And Digital Content	6	8
	1.3 Managing Data, Information And Digital Content	5	6
2. Communication and collaboration	2.1 Interacting Through Digital Technologies	5	8
	2.2 Sharing Through Digital Technologies	4	5
	2.3 Engaging Citizenship Through Digital Technologies	4	5
	2.4 Collaborating Through Digital Technologies	3	3
	2.5 Netiquette	3	3
	2.6 Managing Digital Identity	3	3
3. Digital content creation	3.1 Developing Digital Content	4	7
	3.2 Integrating And Re-Elaborating Digital Content	5	7
	3.3 Copyright And Licences	3	3
	3.4 Programming	1	5
4. Safety	4.1 Protecting Devices	2	2
	4.2 Protecting Personal Data And Privacy	2	2
	4.3 Protecting Health And Well-Being	2	2
	4.4 Protecting The Environment	2	2
5. Problem solving	5.1 Solving Technical Problems	3	7
	5.2 Identifying Needs And Technological Responses	4	7
	5.3 Creatively Using Digital Technology	3	7
	5.4 Identifying Digital Competence Gaps	4	7

Figure 11: Competencies and the minimal levels of proficiency needed to learn ABM using our material and the expected resulting levels of proficiency after doing all tutorials.

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